

Teaching and Learning Methods Based on the Benefits of Generating Predictive Theories for Educational Practices

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Abstract

Educational leadership and management may be considered a "discipline", but it has a brief history marked by turbulence and its future is in doubt. The 1970s to the mid-1990s may seem like a golden age in retrospect. This was in response to a question asked by the Management Editors in Education (Ribbins , 2007a:3). The editors warn potential authors in their call for paper submissions that there is "a lack of confusion and consensus among academics and institutions about the true nature of Educational Leadership and Management as a topic." Due to the rapid changes taking place in the contemporary world, the Higher Education System is now faced with a wide variety of problems. Consequently, there is an urgent need to train more enthusiastic and reflective people in multidisciplinary fields. Therefore, the study and discovery of useful and efficient teaching and learning techniques is one of the most important demands of education systems; Educators play a decisive role in raising such individuals in the sector in question. University is a place where fresh ideas can take root and develop and strong, high roots can be set up. It is a one-of-a-kind location that encompasses all human knowledge. It is a place where people with inventive minds come together, chat with each other and develop new future ideas. In the search for knowledge, preconceptions about what constitutes truth are put to the test. Getting help from knowledgeable instructors who can guide students through all of this can be extremely valuable and productive. The importance given to the education of students as the primary product expected from an education quality system is much more in demand than in the past, given the quality of education. Before making any decision, there has always been a strong emphasis on setting up a link between the two, as well as giving equal attention to the quality of both research and teaching. However, studies have shown that the interest shown in research in universities does not meet the requirements of the quality of education. It is considered important to pay attention to this responsibility in higher education; Therefore, educators should pay attention to learners and learning techniques in their teaching.

Keywords: *Foresight for Educational Practices, Educational Practice Theories, Educational Practices, Benefits of Producing Educational Practices, Teaching and Learning Methods*

1. Introduction

In addition to these two elements, educators must move forward to buy new ways of teaching. In the old system, education was focused on the instructor, and the needs and interests of the students were not considered at any point. At this point, the education given to the students should turn into a technique in which their needs are considered, and the behavior of the students will begin to change actively as a direct result of the lesson. In addition, a sizable part of recent graduates, especially those with undergraduate degrees, do not believe that they are sufficiently prepared to find a job in the sectors in which they were educated. Being dissatisfied with the status quo at any academic institution and then deciding to change it requires a significant amount of work, as well as the support of pioneers and experts associated with that institution. The design is ideal for this research because it gives participants the opportunity to describe their experience using their own words, while focusing on aspects that could lead to an improvement in teaching quality.

The findings of the study were derived directly from the experiences provided by the research participants. The researchers used an inductive method to investigate the codes, categories, and themes. During this method, researchers moved from the specific to the general. The experiences of the participants were considered when developing the ideas or categories that were finally developed. In content analysis, the process begins with the identification of semantic units, then continues with the extraction of relevant codes and the creation of categories according to the similarities between them. The last step is to find themes that can be made even when significant abstraction is present. The traditional method avoids the use of planned classes and instead allows classes and their names to appear naturally from the data.

In addition, a proper description of the data is provided in the study so that other researchers can examine the results and make constructive criticism to increase the strength of the data's transferability. What motivates students most is that they believe in their abilities and respect their

CURRENT SCIENCE

teachers. These children are the future of the nation and besides providing them with information, it should also give them the proper information. "If a teacher is interested in the subject he teaches, he or she will spend more time reviewing relevant authorized texts and keep their knowledge consistently up to date..." Training in metacognition and self-assessment as part of the teaching process is a prerequisite from the instructors' perspectives. "

2. Using Concept Maps and Pre-editors for Classroom Teaching

A prerequisite for teaching from the teacher's perspective is that the material covered in the classroom applies to students' future efforts. Barriers include the absence of a set program, as well as innovative presentations, if possible, by professorial masters. The lack of motivation due to the instructor is an obstacle as well as the lack of interest of the students. Students can gain more motivation, metacognition, and self-confidence after they see that they feel competent to overcome challenges and engage more. The failure of the experts to acknowledge the importance of metacognition and the imperative nature of transferring this knowledge to students as a teacher-related barrier "The need for student-centered teaching is clear; however, the use of these methods cannot be fully implemented for assorted reasons".

"These reasons include the requirement in the teaching curriculum, the substantial number of students in the classrooms, and the vast number of materials and resources." The requirements outline the curriculum to be followed and the materials to be used.

The instructors taking part in this research believed that teaching and learning in higher education is a collaborative process that places equal responsibility on the student and the instructor for the results of the course. In this shared process, higher education must engage students in challenging their preconceptions and models of how the world works so that they can reach a higher level of knowledge. ("PGCAP DAPP141 session 1 - SlideShare") However, students are not always ready for this challenge, and not all are motivated by the desire to understand and apply knowledge. Often, students desire to just survive the course or just learn procedurally to get the highest grades possible before moving on to the next subject as quickly as possible. The most effective teaching

CURRENT SCIENCE

encourages students to challenge the assumptions they make about a topic and helps them be more motivated to learn by placing them in situations where their current model does not work, and they come to see themselves as the author of the answers. This type of teaching helps students question their biases.

3. Presenting the Topics, They Consider to be Important to Students

This shows students that topics they consider important should be presented. In addition, they thought that most industrialized nations looked to implement innovative teaching strategies such as student-centered active techniques, problem-based and project-based approaches in their education system. This method is used in modern times to promote education especially in software engineering and informatics. In the last few years, this initiative has been used to give students more power. They will be allowed to take responsibility for a project and as a result they will have extensive involvement in the software development procedure . Innovative approaches to education have been the subject of considerable research in Iran. For example, Momen Research conducted by Danaie , Noroozi , and Zarshenas has proved a variety of necessary teaching strategies. They also concluded that traditional lecture formats that do not include any feedback to enable students to learn are no longer successful. In addition to improving students' communication abilities, the problem-oriented approach not only contributed to the further development of critical thinking, but also improved students' ability to work effectively and increased their interest in the material they were taught.

In this research, professors pointed out that there are several barriers to successful teaching, including: the curriculum to be followed and the materials to be used in the classroom; in addition, there had to be a considerable number of students, as well as a high volume of theoretical concepts. In the comments made by the faculty members, it was said that "The need for student-centered teaching is obvious , but for some reasons such as the necessity in the teaching curriculum and the substantial number of materials and resources, it is not fully possible to use these methods . "

CURRENT SCIENCE

Specific feelings and dispositions of teachers must develop the type of learning that is kept by students over an extended period. These feelings and attitudes have a significant impact on both their behavior and their teaching.

The design of a classroom's curriculum includes activities such as preparation, successful content delivery, implementation of learning, and evaluation of teaching. A list of functional needs for effective teaching in higher education can be presented based on considerations presented by current research topics. Having a strategy for the classroom and using the most effective teaching tactics According to Choi and Pucker , the most basic function of educators is to organize and manage the teaching process to provide students with the best possible opportunity to receive an all-encompassing education. One of the reasons for the lack of originality in the classroom, according to one member, is that many educators do not have a planned strategy for how to teach and instead simply gather what they are going to teach in one meeting.

4. Using Conceptual Maps and Pre-Organization Plans in Education

Klug and colleagues present several questions and encourage faculty to make it a habit to ask themselves these questions often.

- 1- *Ways to increase the number of impulse students show.*
- 2- *How to instill in children a sense of self-confidence in their ability to solve challenges...*
- 3- *How to train students to organize their own learning activities?*
- 4- *The best way to guide them through the process of doing a self-assessment at the end of each lesson session is...*
- 5- *How to encourage students to work harder in the future by encouraging them now...*
- 6- *What are some ways to supply feedback to students and update them on their own personal development?*

Strategies outlined in lifelong learning, especially in higher education, are increasing the quality of learning through the promotion of education, the use of preliminary organizers and conceptual maps , and the emphasis on student-centeredness. One piece of evidence that the innovative aspects

CURRENT SCIENCE

of programs must be consistently paid off is the idea that creative potential is found in everyone and can be further developed by taking part in proper activities. Of course, in addition to the capabilities, the necessary spaces should be provided so that new concepts can be designed with confidence and purposefully. If this is not the case, new concepts will be difficult to apply, as there will be neither favorable conditions nor favorable causes . During classroom discussions, students will be given the opportunity to understand how to solve problems that may arise in their future careers. Senior instructors strive to engage in self-monitoring and consultation, check their own use of classroom management capabilities, and make action plans to change their practices based on collected data. Instructors meet with colleagues to collect and apply data to assess students' strengths and weaknesses, and then apply procedures to turn students' shortcomings into strengths . The most successful educators regularly check the progress of their students and evaluate how changing teaching strategies have affected the results they achieve with their lessons.

5. Documentation of Experiences

Buying the necessary skills to document the outcomes of the teaching-learning process not only makes management more manageable in terms of reviewing records, but also eases access to up-to-date information. This enables them to have a positive impact on the lives of their students, both personally and professionally. The most effective teachers use differentiated instruction, prove cultural sensitivity, emphasize open communication, supply constructive criticism of students' academic performance, and encourage student development by allowing them to resubmit assignments before grading. These skills can be divided into three categories: This also applies to educators, as having strong research abilities is considered increasingly an essential part of professionalism (Amirova et al., 2020) and a crucial step in development. This is one of the evidence-based teaching techniques (Burke et al., 2005). The purpose of this study is to give case studies of a pedagogical technique known as Teaching Clinic, which aims to increase the perceived importance of addressing methodological challenges in the context of teacher education (Davidson & Palermo, 2015). (TC). During this time, students in teacher education (now known as "students") and applied teachers (now known as "teachers") work together on pedagogical innovations to be

implemented in applied teachers (Baker , 2018). These are examples of service learning in the field of educator preparation and can be seen as such (Stoecker , 2016).

Established educators present research questions about the most pressing issues facing their profession. Students then develop and conduct research projects to find answers to these problems, supported by the evidence they have gathered. The main aim of the study conducted at such a local and practical level is the development of a scientific way of thinking among students. Study abilities are recognized more as tools of professional activity than as something specific to academic research. It is especially important that this point of view is conveyed not only to the students who contribute to the projects, but also to the instructors who deliver their work. While the design requires the choice and construction of interventions in collaboration with practitioners, it supplies only a minimal amount of impact on the situation. This research strategy looks to supply explanations and recommendations about teaching and learning methods that have been shown to be useful, as well as generating theories that may be predictive for educational practice. Researchers engaged in this type of research are often referred to as "didactic engineers" because of the intrusive character of the study (Anderson and Shattuck , 2012; Bakker and Van Eerde , 2015). When it comes to the organizational structure of projects, on a local scale, various initiatives, approaches (e.g., field experiments, statistical analysis, content analysis) as well as a wide variety of data (video recordings, surveys among students, interviews, texts, etc.) are used. Students manage choosing which ones to use, collecting relevant data, and conducting the study.

6. A Series of Guiding Questions Guided by Research Methodologies and Service-Learning

based on a series of guiding questions guided by research methodologies and service-learning. To be more specific , the presentation will include two separate TC projects. Qualitative content analysis (Mayring , 2014) was used as part of this research . (“Teachers’ Beliefs About Subject Specific Competences ... - SpringerLink”) After finishing the learning diary, students were expected to evaluate learning opportunities using a scale from one to five, and to record the actions they took and the difficulties that arose during the execution of the application. Films based on a

CURRENT SCIENCE

topic, specific technical work (programming, mechanics, building, electronics, and applied computer science), external workshops and interviews with companies from the technology sector are some of the learning styles used. After a first review of the data, it was possible to draw some conclusions about the indicator known as "subjectively considered interesting by students". The study showed that when students take part in individual, isolated learning opportunities on climate change, they do not show the expected effect of being intrinsically motivated to buy proper professional skills to explore solutions. These indicators were subjectively found interesting and inspiring by the students taking part in the research. Schools had to close due to COVID-19 and as a result it was impossible to finish the annual curriculum . However, a total of sixteen different courses were designed to fulfill the prerequisites of the study project based on the indicators found. The students used the findings of the qualitative preliminary study as the basis for the hypotheses they developed for the main study conducted using the Mayring (2014) methodological approach. The hypotheses were developed in line with the main research topic.

On the other hand, the DBR technique has been useful in finding these indicators based on various learning formats that students consider subjectively interesting and inspiring. From the Orientation framework (Schreiber & Siegel, 2015) for the "Global Development" learning domain , the "Diagnose-Assess-Act" principal approach has been found to be particularly promising as a pedagogical and didactic core idea.

The service-learning concept presented supplies added resources for the formulation of teaching strategies that are difficult to implement in the regular school year due to the administrative responsibilities and other commitments that teachers assume. This gives instructors a chance not only to gain ideas for the design of the lessons, but also to further develop their own teaching based on sound and up-to-date scientific technique. According to reports, participants learned new strategies to "excite children with fresh ideas and show them that STEM can't be just theoretical," and it is crucial for students and society alike. In assessing students' ability to research, reflect, and critically analyze scientific knowledge from a variety of perspectives, teachers placed considerable weight on the connection between the two concepts. Developing as autonomous and responsible individuals primarily requires the appreciation of principles such as sustainability, environmental awareness, and solidarity. In addition, students' participation in the environmental and social

challenges of the 21st century has resulted in a marked increase in interest in career profiles of the technical and scientific fields.

In addition, this project gives them the opportunity to interact with their research methodologies in a way that is not only challenging but inspiring. This is a sometimes-overlooked part of teacher education. They were able to put several teaching approaches into practice and then methodically analyze these pathways using scientific methodologies. As a result, a deeper knowledge is gained about the important symbiosis that exists between theoretical work and real classroom teaching (Paran, 2017). It is likely that future studies will seek to explore the impact of different service-learning methods on students' motivation levels (cf. Medina & Gordon, 2014; Huber, 2015). On the other hand, it is possible to notice a reframing of a teacher's subjective role feeling in the sense of transformational learning (Mezirow & Taylor, 2009). Graduate students taking part in a minimum grade project will find it particularly beneficial to collaborate with other instructors who are already practicing. To begin with, these unique conditions make it possible for them to gain practical experience and benefit from the ability of the trainers, in addition to the required practice.

7. Students Benefit from Initiatives

Children's benefit from initiatives by other educators and students in other classes depends on the impression that their work is important and valuable. Thanks to the atmosphere they were in, they were able to gain experience in research methodologies and applied teaching, which would not have been possible if the course had been structured differently. On the other hand, students were able to gain valuable real-world experiences by taking part in extracurricular activities outside the institution.

Students get an extra boost of motivation from their work in local schools, which encourages them to further develop their pedagogical and didactic ability in a practical context based on real school challenges. Also, the interaction of the scientific approach with practical school experiences enables students to internalize their own values for contemporary teaching to prepare for their

CURRENT SCIENCE

future role as teachers. This is because students are exposed to both the scientific approach and firsthand school experience.

Given the widespread emphasis on education as a means by which nations and individuals can achieve their ends, it should come as no surprise that a significant amount of work has been focused on finding which forms of education best allow education to achieve its goals. While education encompasses a wide range of issues, including education policy and management, the structure of educational institutions, the management of educational institutions' finances, and the leadership of educational institutions, effective teaching is ultimately the most important factor determining the success of education systems (eg Barber & Mourshed, 2007; Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012; Hattie, 2003; OECD, 2016; Stigler & Hiebert, 2009). Starting from various theoretical perspectives, many studies have tried to find answers to the question of how classroom teaching should be organized to be as effective as possible (Hattie, 2009). As a direct result of this, there are more studies evaluating the usefulness or relevance of various teaching strategies. Making such assessments is a logical method for synthesizing results and inferences from many studies. Systematic research reviews have the potential to make several contributions to the knowledge that underlies research, clinical practice, and policy decisions (cf. Gough, Thomas, & Oliver, 2012).

However, findings from underlying studies often show mixed results and sometimes even contradictory findings that can be attributed to a wide variety of factors (e.g., Shute, 2008). The effects of teaching techniques and interventions depend not only on the context, but also on the way they are implemented and enacted, and the people who apply them. This is because teaching methods and interventions work within complex systems (cf. Cartwright and Hardie, 2012; Pawson, 2006; Pawson, Greenhalgh, Harvey, and Walshe, 2005; Rycroft-Malone et al., 2012). There is inevitably a certain amount of decontextualization involved in trying to synthesize the findings and implications of many primary studies. Despite this, researchers at the secondary research level accept, relate, and/or problematize the meaning and impact of context in various ways. We are particularly curious about whether and how questions about who finds success and under what conditions are problematic (cf. Pawson, 2006). As a result, we explore these recurring

challenges. In research evaluations of different teaching approaches, it is important to focus on how they relate to the conflict that exists between specificity and breadth of practice.

8. Format of Overview

This work was undertaken in the context of a broader research study whose overall aim was to broaden and deepen our understanding of educational practice and educational research (Hirsh & Nilholm , 2019; Roman, Sundberg , Hirsh , Nilholm , & Forsberg , 2018). Below is a summary of the starting points and assumptions guiding the entire research effort (see Nilholm & Goransson , 2017). The purpose of this is to supply clarity about the context in which the current work appears. Research reviews are considered secondary because they summarize and synthesize primary research findings on a particular topic. In turn, this paves the way for a higher-level study known as tertiary research that summarizes and synthesizes research reviews (Polanin , Maynard, & Dell, 2017). Review of reviews (Maag , 2006), tertiary review (Torgerson , 2007), mega- analysis (Terhart , 2011), and umbrella review are some of the terms used to describe the type of tertiary research that uses research. These terms include overview (Polanin et al., 2017), meta-meta-analysis (Hattie , 2009; Kazrin , Durac , & Agteros , 1979), meta-synthesis ((Grant & Booth , 2009), which may be the variable used but is consistent One thing is that the tertiary level aims to synthesize evidence on a particular topic of interest by examining the highest level of evidence, which is only the evidence presented in systematic reviews or meta-analyses.

The idea that it is useful for the research community to map and analyze research that it considers relevant (see Nilholm & Goransson , 2017) is the main starting point. As a result, we only include research that is good :

- a) *diverse types of second-level review research methodologies,*
- b) *the scrutiny level (including scrutiny from critical interpretative perspectives) and*
- c) *maps and analysis, topics studied, theorems, etc. various aspects of a research field such as*

CURRENT SCIENCE

overview method and those focused on evidence extraction is that our method covers diverse types of second-level review research methodologies, However, a single piece of paper cannot detail all these factors. Therefore, the focus of the current research is on the findings and conclusions provided, with special emphasis on the emerging conflict between contextualization and generalizability .

Also, unless such assessments are specifically linked to school interventions or curricula , not including reports on students' and teachers' health and well-being, as well as their self-perceptions and self-efficacy levels, including several studies on the teaching use of technological artifacts makes many of these reviews a To some extent, it has led to discussions of external learning environments (outside classrooms and schools).

This has led to further analysis, driven by a general interest in inductively and more deeply exploring the most often occurring problems, to find recurring problems and to group problem patterns into categories. This leads to further research (see Saini & Shlonsky , 2012; Thomas & Harden , 2008). In the analysis phase, the abstracts were treated as text excerpts and subjected to qualitative content analysis. Content analysis is a technique that can be used to flexibly analyze text data (Cavanagh , 1997; Kondracki and Wellman , 2002). What Downe-Wamboldt (1992, p. 314) states as the purpose of content analysis is " to present information and insight into the phenomenon under study" . This is conducted by methodically classifying data and detecting patterns (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005).

Regardless of the type of text from which the starting point for content analysis is taken, the analysis begins at the open level. After that, it is possible that it progresses to the hidden level, although this is not always the case. Explicit analysis focuses on the content aspect of the text and finds components that are already clear (Downe-Rambolt , 1992; Kondracki et al., 2002). Implicit analysis, on the other hand, focuses on the meanings hidden beneath the surface of the text (Downe-Wamboldt , 1992; Kondracki and Wellman , 2002). When compiling a summary of the findings and reflections of each of the reviews undertaken in the early phase of the coding process, our overarching goal is to do so at an explicit level, with as little room for interpretation or abstraction as possible.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Graneheim and Lundman (2004) in this study served as a compass for the later inductive review of summaries. According to Coffey and Atkinson (1996, p. 32), codes are "tools to think with" and "heuristic tools" that enable data to be designed in many and/or new ways (while still being at the level of open data) .

In the next section on results, we refer to our overarching categories as "overview findings" (with associated subcategories). An overview finding is the result of a cumulative analysis of individual review findings describing a phenomenon or characteristics of a phenomenon (in this case, teaching techniques). An overview finding can be considered the product of a cumulative analysis (cf. Lewin et al., 2015).

In general, the conclusions drawn from a broad overview can be expressed at various levels of abstraction, depending on the degree of interpretation made. The findings of an overview at a lower level of abstraction are close to studies that usually support them and are formulated with concepts derived directly from those studies, whereas findings of an overview at a higher level of abstraction may require. Additionally, it served as partial guidance for the approach incorporated into the CERQual (meaning reliance on evidence from qualitative research reviews) framework outlined by Lewin et al . Supplying a mechanism for systematically and openly assessing the significance (for consistency) of results from qualitative research is one of the key aims of the leadership educator initiative.

Although our primary interest is in finding recurring patterns and leading a troubling discussion about these patterns, we recognize the importance (for consistency) of visualizing the occurrence and frequency of various aspects (which together form our overview findings) across various baseline studies. This serves as a sign of the importance of visualizing the occurrence and frequency of various aspects.

9. Conclusion

Graham and Hebert (2011) conclude: It is not possible to say with certainty that a writing intervention will succeed in all other circumstances just because it is successful in curing. There

CURRENT SCIENCE

is rarely an exact match between the conditions under which the research was conducted and the conditions in which it was after conducted by the teachers. (“Reviews of teaching methods – which fundamental issues are identified?”) This is because the research was conducted in a controlled environment. It can vary depending on factors such as discrepancies between the conditions in which a practice is practiced by the teacher and its effectiveness as determined by researchers, differences among students (such as reading or writing skills, dispositions, and previous academic achievement), differences in practice (the number of students in a class and what is available to them). such as financial resources). The abilities of those who practice teaching (for example, beliefs about teaching and learning , success in classroom management, and experiences from teaching writing and teaching) have been synthesized in several reviews, particularly those published in the last decade, with the study of the use of technological artifacts in teaching. All these considerations come to the same conclusion as Smetana and Bell (2012): Although computer simulations show great promise in the field of scientific education, none of them is guaranteed. Computer simulations , like any other pedagogical tool, have the potential to be useful when they are of high enough quality and applied correctly. Therefore, the right question for academics to ask is often not whether simulation can produce the intended effects; The main question to be asked is how lecturers and students use simulations. In this study, barriers by code were divided into two main categories: professor-related barriers and regulation-related ones; For these reasons, full use of these methods is not possible. However, teachers who are aware of the necessity of student participation for a better understanding of the content try to use this method as a combination of classroom speech presentation and involving students in teaching and learning . This result is Momen Danaei et al. (10), Zarshenas et al. (12) and Noroozi (11). To make teaching methods more effective, the necessary conditions should be found in the behavior of the faculties. This category appeared from some code, including having a lesson plan ; the use of proper educational strategies and metacognition training and students' self-assessment during instruction; use of concept and pre-organizer maps in education, knowledge; and explaining how to solve problems in professional careers through teaching discussion, documentation of experience, and satisfying interaction with students go with these results. This result Klug et al ., Byun et al. and Consistent with the findings of Khanyfr et al. Additionally, and from the results, we can conclude

CURRENT SCIENCE

that a major challenge for universities, especially at a time of resource constraints, is to organize teaching in a way that maximizes learning effectiveness. (“Effective Teaching Methods in Higher Education: Requirements and ...”) As mentioned earlier, the biggest barrier to change is that many faculty members are not trained for teaching roles and are ignorant of the research literature on effective pedagogy. These findings are in line with Knapper's research , which says that the best ideas for effective teaching include the following, and there is a need for much more literature on this subject, especially in Turkish.

“ Teaching methods that focus on student activity and task performance rather than just getting facts; Opportunities for meaningful personal interaction between students and teachers ; Opportunities for collaborative team learning; More specific assessment methods emphasizing task performance in natural situations, preferably with peer and self-assessment elements; Making learning processes more open and encouraging students to reflect on how they learn; Learning tasks that encourage the integration of knowledge and skills from different fields .”

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